

Proving the antimicrobial therapeutic activity on a new copper thiosemicarbazone complex

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KEYWORDS.

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ABSTRACT

The misuse and overdose of antimicrobial medicines are fostering the emergence of novel drug-resistant pathogens, providing negative repercussions not only on the global healthcare system due to the rise of long-term or chronic patients and inefficient therapies, but also, to the world trade, productivity and, in short, to the global economic growth. In view of these scenario, novel action plans to constrain this antibacterial resistance are needed. Thus, given the proven antiproliferative tumoral and microbial features of thiosemicarbazone (TSCN) ligands, we have here synthesized a novel effective antibacterial copper–thiosemicarbazone complex, demonstrating both its solubility profile and complex stability under physiological conditions, along with their safety and antibacterial activity in contact with human cellular nature and 2-most predominant bacterial strains, respectively. A significant growth inhibition (17% after 20 h) was evidenced over the time, paving the way towards an effective antibacterial therapy based on these copper-TSCN complexes.

NOMENCLATURE

TSCN: thiosemicarbazone, AMR: antimicrobial resistance, GDP: gross domestic product; SDG: sustainable development goal, AMC: antimicrobial consumption, ROS: reactive oxygen species, H₂L: N1-(4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene)-N4-(4-nitrophenyl)thiosemicarbazone, *logP*: partition coefficient logarithm of drug candidates in a lipophilic / hydrophilic phases (oil:water), ADME: absorption, distribution, metabolism & excretion, EC: *Escherichia coli*, SA: *Staphylococcus aureus*, CH₂Cl₂: Dichloromethane, EtOH: ethanol, DMSO: Dimethyl sulfoxide, NMR: Nuclear magnetic resonance, AcOH: acetic acid, SIdI: interdepartmental investigation service, TMS: tetramethylsilane, FAB: fast atom bombardment, MALDI: matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization, IR: infrared, ATR: attenuated total reflectance, DMSO: dimethyl sulfoxide, NaOH: sodium hydroxide, Cu(ClO₄)₂: copper(II) perchlorate, H₂O: water, MeOH: methanol, PBS: phosphate-buffered solution, HEWL: hen egg white lysozyme, MTT: (3-(4, 5-dimethylthiazolyl-2)-2, 5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide, ATCC: American type culture collection, DMEM: Dulbecco's modified Eagle medium, RPMI: Roswell Park Memorial Institute medium, FBS: fetal bovine serum, EDTA: ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, CECT: Spanish type Microbial culture collection, NB: nutrient Broth, OD: optical density, ZOI: zone of inhibition, CFU: colony-forming units, FDA: fluorescein diacetate staining, H₂DCF-DA: 2',7'-dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate, CLSM: confocal laser scanning microscopy, PI: propidium iodide, SD: standard deviation, GLASS: global antimicrobial resistance and use surveillance system, MIC: minimum inhibitory concentration.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the top 10 global public health threats facing humanity is the antimicrobial resistance (AMR), since the misuse and overdose of antimicrobial medicines are currently driving the appearance of novel drug-resistant pathogens, which could compromise crucial areas such as global health, food safety & security, economic growth, poverty alleviation or, even, the environment.¹ This fact, in turn, impacts not only into a raised emergence of untreatable common diseases (*e.g.* urinary infections, sepsis, diarrhea) but also into larger life-saving medical procedures (*e.g.* ventilation, tube feeding, dialysis) riskier to be performed. This infection resistance has been also aggravated by the absence of new antibiotics on the pipeline market, resulting in long-term or chronic patients and inefficient therapies along with a high mortality index: in 2020, >800.000 people at all

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3 ages were infected in Europe (with 30% of pediatric patients; ~200.000 newborns), killing
4 on average of 35.000 people *per year*.² Thus, this circumstance led to
5 significant economic burden not only on the European healthcare system (estimated in ~
6 €1.1 billion *per year*) but also into the global economy, international trade, healthcare, or
7 productivity. Recently, the World Bank has estimated that, if AMR is not addressed, by
8 2050 the global economy may have lost ~4% of annual gross domestic product
9 (GDP), facing an estimated total cost of USD 100 trillion.³ Given this ongoing
10 situation and its future forecasting, European Commission has included a new
11 Sustainable Development Goal (SDGs) indicator, proposing recommended actions for
12 fighting the AMR by 2030, as for instance i) the creation of national plans for
13 monitoring the antimicrobial consumption (AMC), ii) the improvement of the
14 infection prevention, iii) the promotion of novel research and innovation plans or,
15 even, iv) the inspiration of the awareness raising among health professionals &/or the
16 general public.

17 Thus, there are still plenty of room for the improvement against this emerged pathological
18 scenario. Some thiosemicarbazone (TSCN) copper (Cu)-containing complexes have been
19 already tested for this purpose, focusing on a broad range of respiratory tract pathogens
20 by delivering Cu ions efficiently into the infected cells cytoplasm.⁴ In fact, just the TSCN
21 has been used for the treatment of diverse human diseases, including cancer^{5,6}
22 or tuberculosis.⁷ Related compounds such as *p*-acetamidobenzaldehyde
23 thiosemicarbazone (amithionoz®) already at the 2nd World War (in Africa & South
24 America), showed bacteriostatic efficiency on *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* in
25 combination with the isoniazid,⁸ and in general those TSCN with better lipophilicity
26 and available binding sites showed the best performance (**Figure 1a**, binding sites
27 highlighted in yellow)⁵ Thereafter, this TSCN's effectiveness has been improved in
28 some cases with copper metalation (mononuclear complexes; **Figure 1.b**; X: Cl
29 and dinuclear compounds; **Figure 1c**; Y=SO₄)⁹ achieving even synthetic fibers with
30 excellent growth inhibition by grafting antibacterial copper TSCNs onto cellulose
31 (**Figure 1b**; X:OH).¹⁰

32 The experimental data about the TSCN complexes' mechanism and stability in
33 physiological solution are quite scarce, despite their efficacy has been generally
34 reported mostly for mononuclear tridentate complexes (**Figure 1c**; X:OH, Cl, and even
35 bipy¹¹ &/or some dinuclear (**Figure 1b**, Y: μ -SO₄,⁹ μ -Cl,¹²), which has been ascribed
36 to the lessening of the metal toxicity: turning to more lipophilic character (*i.e.*
37 bithiosemicarbazones)⁴, higher is the dual metal & ligand release. This action leads to³

an antibacterial effect:¹³ increase of reactive oxygen species (ROS) generation,¹⁴ associated with potential DNA damage¹⁵ and also binding with target antibacterial proteins (**Figure 1d**; R is aromatic¹² but also with aliphatic¹⁶). From the recent literature, the substitution at the terminal N4 group of the TSCN seems to boost the complex lipophilicity, enabling a greater diffusion through the lipid bacterial wall and, in turn, enhancing the antibacterial activity with lower side effects¹² No other structure-activity relationship or other obvious additional role of copper complexes have been clearly established from the reported data up to now. This is a clear indication of the need of a more detailed comparison from the variety of examples with these molecules, their complexes and the methodologies used in the antibacterial analysis.¹⁷

Figure 1. Thiosemicarbazone and copper complexes with similar structures and antibacterial activity.

In view of the above, the actual social needs and our previous experience producing effective anticancer complexes by using TSCN by a groove-binding model,¹⁸ we propose here an innovative antimicrobial copper therapeutic agent based on a similar TSCN with N4 substitution, **H₂L** (N1-(4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene)-N4-(4-nitrophenyl)thiosemicarbazone, **Figure 1**). In this respect, the antibacterial efficacy of this Cu(HL)₂ complex is evaluated using two diverse strains, widely recognized as appellant

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3 human pathogenic models with broadly propagation features: i) *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*;
4 EC), main representative of Gram-negative bacterial strains resistant to 3rd generation
5 cephalosporins; and ii) *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*; SA), a Gram-positive strain,
6 part of our own skin flora and with a frequent occurrence in healthcare facilities. Among
7 others, it creates resistance against the medicine methicillin, a derivative of the popular
8 penicillin (*e.g.* sensitive infected patients are more likely to decrease in 64% times higher
9 than non-resistant ones).¹⁹ In addition, we report our findings from the studies of the
10 solution profile of this Cu-TSCN complex in biological media, its integrity and *in vitro*
11 biosafety character, which is crucial for reliable and reproducibility data.
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19 2. EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

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21 **2.1. Methods:** NMR spectra were recorded at room temperature, using a two-channel
22 300 MHz Bruker Avance III-HD Nanobay spectrometer equipped with a 5 mm BBO
23 1H/X probe and Z gradients, located at Interdepartmental Investigation Service (SIdI).
24 DMSO-d₆ was used as the solvent (containing 0.05% (v/v) tetramethylsilane (TMS) as a
25 reference). Chemical shift values are given in ppm relative to the residual TMS signals.
26 The following abbreviations were used: s (singlet), d (doublet) and m (multiplet).
27 Elemental analyses were performed on a LECO CHNS-932 elemental analyzer located at
28 SIdI. Mass spectra were recorded using fast atom bombardment (FAB) in a Waters VG
29 AutoSpec mass spectrometry unit; and using matrix-assisted laser desorption/ionization
30 (MALDI) with a Bruker Ultraflex III (MALDI-TOF/TOF) mass spectrometry unit, both
31 located at SIdI. Infrared (IR) spectra were recorded using a PerkinElmer Model 283
32 spectrometer with an attenuated total reflectance (ATR) MIRacle Single Reflection
33 Horizontal accessory and equipped with CsI optical windows for spectra between 600
34 and 200 cm⁻¹ in Nujol mull preparations. Absorbance spectra were recorded using a
35 Thermo Evolution 220 spectrophotometer to record the UV-visible, equipped with
36 temperature control within ±0.1 °C.
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48 For particle size and ζ-potential determinations, each complex was diluted from the
49 DMSO stock (5 mM) with the desired media (aqueous solution, cell culture media-*see*
50 *section 3*, nutrient broth-NB medium, composed by 5 g·L⁻¹ beef extract, 10 g·L⁻¹ peptone,
51 5 g·L⁻¹ NaCl, pH=7-7.2), being analyzed with a Malvern Nano-ZS, Zetasizer Nano series.
52 Once the suspensions were prepared, an ultrasonication step followed (ultrasound tip at
53 10% amplitude for 1 min), monitoring the particle size evolution from t = 0 to 24 h. The
54 studies were performed with 1% DMSO (v/v) in the final solution.
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2.2. H₂L Synthesis:

2.2.1. Precursor: *p*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide was prepared following a reported procedure²⁰ with slight changes in the purification procedure. Briefly, on a suspension of *p*-nitrophenylisothiocyanate (1.0043 g, 5.57 mmol) in acetonitrile (20 mL) cooled in an ice bath, a solution of hydrazine hydrate (541.8 μ L, 11.1 mmol) in acetonitrile (15 mL) was added dropwise and the reaction was kept with constant stirring for 1 hour, obtaining a brown solid that was filtered, washed with acetonitrile and vacuum dried. The product was purified by chromatography in silica gel, using as eluents CH₂Cl₂ and CH₂Cl₂:EtOH 99:1. The final product was eluted last and concentrated to dryness, isolating 712.6 mg of a yellow solid. Yield: 60%. FAB⁺-MS(m/z): [M+CH₃CN]⁺: 253. ¹H-RMN (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆), δ (ppm): 8.07 (d, 2H, H₆); 8.21 (d, 2H, H₇); 10.26 (s, 1H, N-H₂); 10.76 (s, 1H, N-H₄). ¹³C-RMN (DMSO-d₆), δ (ppm): 123.45 (C₇), 123.70 (C₆), 143.06 (C₈), 145.45 (C₅), 175.74 (C₃). IR (cm⁻¹): ν_a (NH₂): 3336; ν_s (NH₂): 3241; ν (NH): 3211; δ (NH₂): 1637; ν_a (NO₂): 1506; ν_s (NO₂): 1334; ν (C=S): 848 (**Figure S1**. NMR numbering)

2.2.2. H₂L:N1-(4-(dimethylamino)benzylidene)-N4-(4-nitrofenil)thiosemi carbazone: H₂L was prepared following a reported procedure²⁰ with important variations that are described as follows: an ethanolic solution (1.5 mL) of *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (11.3 mg, 0.076 mmol) was added dropwise to a solution of *p*-nitrophenylthiosemicarbazide (16.1 mg, 0.076 mmol) in AcOH 6% (2 mL) at 50°C. The mixture was stirred and heated to reflux temperature for 5 h. An orange solid was isolated after cooling by filtration and washed several times with very cold portions (5 mL) of ethanol and cold methanol. Finally, the solid (17.2 mg) was recrystallized into CH₂Cl₂, filtered and vacuum dried. Yield: 66%. Orange solid. Elemental Analysis (%) for C₁₆H₁₇N₅O₂S·H₂O: Calculated: C, 53.17; H, 5.30; N, 19.38. Experimental: C, 52.51; H, 4.81; N, 19.27. FAB⁺-MS (m/z): [M]⁺: 343.2; [M+H]⁺: 344.2. ¹H-RMN (300 MHz, DMSO-d₆), δ (ppm): 2.98 (s, 6H, H₁₁); 6.74 (d, 2H, H₉); 7.70 (d, 2H, H₈); 8.10 (d, 3H, H₂ and H₆); 8.23 (d, 2H, H₃); 10.29 (s, 1H, N-HA); 11.96 (s, 1H, N-HB). ¹³C-RMN (DMSO-d₆), δ (ppm): 39.52 (C₁₁), 111.59 (C₉), 120.70 (C₇), 123.59 (C₂), 123.64 (C₃), 129.31 (C₈), 143.13 (C₁), 145.25 (C₆), 145.62 (C₄), 151.75 (C₁₀), 174.03 (C₅). IR (cm⁻¹): ν (NH): 3254, 3118; ν (C=N): 1611; ν_a (NO₂): 1501; ν_s (NO₂): 1330; ν (C=S): 843 (**Figure S1**. NMR numbering).

2.3. Synthesis of the Cu complex:

H₂L (50.06 mg, 0.146 mmol) was suspended in methanol (50 mL) and NaOH (0.1M) solution was added until the mixture turned into a clear solution of pH 9. Then, a solution of Cu(ClO₄)₂·6 H₂O (39.41 mg, 0.106 mmol) in 5 mL of methanol (caution! perchlorates can cause explosions when heated) was added dropwise and at room temperature. The reaction mixture was stirred for 24 h, turning from olive green to dark brown. The solid obtained was filtered, washed with water and MeOH, and vacuum dried (40.89 mg). The recrystallization of the compound in DMSO afforded monocrystals suitable for X-ray diffraction. [Cu(HL)₂]. Brown solid. Yield: 75%. Single crystals were obtained from DMSO solution of the pure complex. Elemental Analysis (%) for C₃₂H₃₂N₁₀O₄S₂Cu·4H₂O: Calculated: C, 46.85; H, 4.91; N, 17.07. Experimental: C, 47.06; H, 4.27; N, 16.98. IR (cm⁻¹): ν (NH): 3392; ν (C=N): 1606; ν_a (NO₂): 1482; ν_s (NO₂): 1323; ν (C-S): 807. Lattice water molecules bands at ν: 3550-3200 cm⁻¹; δ: 1630-1600 cm⁻¹; and librational modes: 600-200 cm⁻¹. TGA analysis indicates one water molecule releases at 175 °C & decomposition through 175-400°C.

2.4. Crystallography data.

Data were collected on a Bruker Kappa Apex II diffractometer. A summary of the crystal data, experimental details and refinement results is listed in

Table 1. The software package SHELXTL was used for space group determination, structure solution, and refinement.²¹ The structure was solved by direct methods, completed with difference Fourier syntheses, and refined with anisotropic displacement parameters.

Table 1. Crystal data, experimental details, and refinement results for the crystal resolution of Cu(HL)₂.

Compound		[Cu(HL) ₂]	
Chemical formula		C ₃₆ H ₄₄ CuN ₁₀ O ₆ S ₄	
Formula weight (g mol⁻¹)		904.59	
Temperature (K)		200(2)	
Crystal system		Triclinic	
Wavelength (Å)		0.71073	
Space group		P-1	
Crystal size (mm³)		0.046 x 0.056 x 0.156	
a (Å)	α (°)	12.6904(5)	103.4707(18)
b (Å)	β (°)	13.1423(4)	110.8505(18)
c (Å)	γ (°)	13.8468(5)	93.2278(18)
Volume (Å³)	Z	2074.00(13)	2
Density, calculated (g/cm³)		1.449	
Absorption coefficient (mm⁻¹)		0.785	

F(000)	942
θ range for data collection (°)	1.61 – 25.35
Reflections collected	94931
Independent reflections	7569 [R(int) = 0.1246]
Coverage of independent collections	99.6%
Data/restraints/parameters	7569 / 6 / 530
Goodness of fit on F²	1.064
Final R indices [I > 2σ(I)] / all data	R1 = 0.0488 / 0.1015 wR2 = 0.1114 / 0.1357
Largest diff. peak and hole, (e Å⁻³)	0.448 and -0.406

*All details can be found in CCDC 2119427, which contain the supplementary crystallographic data for this paper. These data can be obtained free of charge from The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Center via <https://summary.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/structure-summary-form>.

2.5. Lipophilicity measurements:

The lipophilicity of the compound was determined by measuring their log *P* in a *n*-octanol/Tris-buffered aqueous solution with a pH of 7.40. The ligand H₂L and the corresponding Cu complex were dissolved in *n*-octanol (previously saturated with the aqueous buffer), and the same volume of aqueous buffer (presaturated with octanol) was added to the *n*-octanol. The samples were thoroughly mixed with stirring for 1 h and, then, the two phases were separated by means of centrifugation at 6000 rpm for 5 min. Following the phase separation, UV-Vis spectra of the compounds were recorded in both the *n*-octanol and aqueous phases. These spectra were then compared to those of the original *n*-octanol stock solutions. Experiments were carried out in triplicate and the log *P* values of the compounds were determined using the following **Equation (X)**.

$$\log P = \log \frac{[\text{compound}]_{\text{oct}}}{[\text{compound}]_{\text{water}}} = \log \left(\frac{A_{\text{oct}}}{A_{\text{aqu.}}} \right) \text{ (X)}$$

2.6. Structural stability:

2.6.1. *UV-Visible monitoring in buffer solution.*

The compound was initially dissolved in DMSO (5 mM). For all experiments, the desired concentration of complexes was achieved by dilution of the stock DMSO solution with Tris-HCl aqueous buffer to reach concentration of complex from 10⁻⁶ to 10⁻⁴ M. All the solutions and buffers were adjusted to pH 7.40 and 37°C. The studies were performed with 1% DMSO (v/v) in the final solution.

2.6.2. *UV/Vis kinetics experiments with HEWL (hen egg white lysozyme).*

To investigate the interaction of complex Cu(HL)₂ with model proteins, electronic spectra of the protein model HEWL at 3.33·10⁻⁶ M dissolved in Tris-HCl (pH 7) were recorded. The typical absorbance of proteins at 280 nm was monitored before and after the addition

of complex $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ using 2.5% of DMSO, at a stoichiometric ratio of 3:1 (metal to protein) for 24 h at room temperature. The binding affinity constants were calculated as a pseudo-first order based on the equal results obtained for stoichiometry: 10:1 and 3:1 for both cases.

2.7. Cyclic voltammetry:

Cyclic voltammetry assays were carried out in a three-electrode cell: 1 & 2-platinum as the working & counter electrodes and 3-Ag/AgCl containing KCl (3M) as reference electrode. Measurements were performed at room temperature using a biopotentiostat ($\mu\text{Stat 400}$ Bipotentiostat/Galvanostat STAT400). Deaeration of solutions was accomplished by passing a stream of nitrogen through the solution for 10 min prior to the measurement, maintaining a blanket N_2 atmosphere over the solution during the measurement. The potentials were measured using a 10^{-3} M solution of complex in a mixture of solvents of DMF/ PBS (2:1 v/v) at pH 7.4 containing 0.10 M of $[\text{n-Bu}_4\text{N}][\text{BF}_4]$ as supporting electrolyte.

2.8. Safety: Cell culture and cellular viability (MTT assay):

Human colon (Caco-2, ATCC HTB-37TM) carcinoma cell line and the promyelocytic cell line HL-60 (ATCC[®]CCL-240TM) were maintained in DMEM (the first cell line) and RPMI medium (last one), respectively, supplemented with glutamax-1 with 10% of heated-inactivated FBS, 1% penicillin/streptomycin, 1% L-glutamine and 1% non-essential amino acids. Both cell lines were routinely grown at 37 °C in a humidified 5% CO_2 atmosphere. Media was changed twice *per* week and cells were passaged at 80% of confluence (cell density at 8×10^4 , $\sim 1 \times 10^5$ cells *per* cm^2), being harvested by trypsinization (1% trypsin-EDTA solution).

The cytotoxic activity of $[\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2]$ complex as well as its precursors (91.55% of H_2L and 8.5 % of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, respectively) were analyzed by the colorimetric MTT (3-(4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay. The adherent colon cell line (Caco-2 cells) and the suspension HL-60 cells were seeded 24 h prior to the assay in 96-well plates at a density of 1×10^5 cells *per* well in supplemented culture media. The complex suspensions were prepared as a dilution series with cell culture media described as follows: 30 μL of each complex (from a stock prepared at 1% DMSO aqueous solution (v/v)), were added to a final volume of 300 μL *per* well, yielding different concentrations ranging from 10 to 0.08 μM (in triplicate). Moreover, a set of diverse control wells was left on each plate: i) medium without cells, ii) cells with a cytotoxic agent (Triton), iii)

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3 untreated cells and iv) cells containing medium with the same concentration of DMSO
4 (DMSO control). Subsequently, all these treatments were added into the cells for 72 h,
5 while being kept at 37 °C with a 5% CO₂ atmosphere. The cytotoxicity was determined
6 by adding the MTT reactant (0.5 mg·mL⁻¹ in PBS, incubated at 37 °C for 2 h) followed
7 by a PBS washing with 100 μL, ending with 100 μL of DMSO added to each well.
8 Absorbance was determined at λ= 539 nm under stirring. The percentage of cell viability
9 was calculated by the absorbance measurements of control growth and test growth in the
10 presence of the formulations at various concentration levels.
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17 **2.9. Antibacterial Activity:**

18 Two standard bacterial strains were used as representative of Gram-positive type, *S.*
19 *aureus*-SA (CECT 240, strain designation ATCC 6538P) and Gram-negative, *E. coli*-EC
20 (CECT 516, strain designation ATCC 8739) for the antibacterial performance, preserved
21 at -80°C in glycerol (20% v/v) until their use. For their reactivation, 1 mL of each
22 inoculum were resuspended in nutrient broth under stirring conditions (NB, 20 mL, 37°C,
23 100 rpm), being routinely tracked by measuring optical density (OD) at 600 nm
24 (Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer) in order to preserve the exponentially phase of
25 each microorganism during the total contact time (20 h). In particular, diverse
26 concentrations of [Cu(HL)₂] solutions (0, 13, 17, 33, 67, 100, 134 μM) were prepared as
27 well as control samples (H₂L ligand and CuCl₂·2H₂O), being dissolved over 2.4 mL of
28 the previously mentioned 10⁶ cells·mL⁻¹ inoculums of a 24-well plate. In the case of the
29 controls, for each desired concentration, the quantity of each constituent was adjusted to
30 the corresponding part of the bulk unit (*e.g.*, 17 μM of [Cu(HL)₂] corresponds to 15.4 μM
31 of H₂L + 4.0 μM of CuCl₂·2H₂O. After 20 h of incubation at 37°C under static conditions,
32 the *bacterial viability* was evaluated by determining 2 parameters:
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44 A) colony-forming units (CFU), where 10-fold serial bacteria dilutions in PBS were
45 placed in sterile 96 well plates. Replicated 10 μL spots were placed on Petri dishes
46 containing NB agar-medium, counting after 24 h the CFU using a CL-1110 counting
47 instrument (Acequilabs, Spain). For colony number estimations, at least three replicates
48 of at least two serial dilutions were considered in order to obtain an estimated inhibition
49 (CFU·mL⁻¹);
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54 B) fluorescein diacetate staining (FDA) is a non-fluorescent compound, extensively used
55 as indicator for *S. aureus* / *E. coli* enzymatic activity determination due to its ability to
56 turn to a green fluorescent agent (fluorescein) once metabolized by functional cells. Thus,
57 this enzymatic conversion was analyzed in 96-well black microplates by mixing 5 μL of
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3 FDA ($2 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$ in DMSO) with $195 \mu\text{L}$ of bacterial suspension in each well. The plate
4 was incubated at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 30 min, with continuous readings every 5 min ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 485 \text{ nm}$;
5 $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 538 \text{ nm}$) using a fluorometer (Fluoroskan Ascent FL Fluorimeter/Luminometer;
6 Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). The possible fluorescence interference of the
7 culture medium and $[\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2]$ was also checked.²² Each sample was measured for
8 quadruple, disclosing the outcomes as an inhibition percentage, normalizing the
9 difference of the sample fluorescent intensity with the control blank assays.

10 Moreover, the fluorometer was also used for the determination of the bacterial oxidation
11 (ROS production).^{23,24} Briefly, $150 \mu\text{L}$ of each sample fraction were incubated for 30
12 min in 96-well black microplates with $50 \mu\text{L}$ of $10 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ of the ROS salt (2',7'-
13 dichlorodihydrofluorescein diacetate, $\text{H}_2\text{DCF-DA}$), which is sensitive for hydrogen
14 peroxide and other oxidative species, including hydroxyl and peroxy radicals. Each
15 sample was measured for quadruple readings, every 5 min ($\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 495 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 525 \text{ nm}$)
16 and represented normalized with respect to the negative control group for a direct
17 comparison.

18 Confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM) was performed for visual and qualitative
19 assessment of antibacterial performances. Cell images of each bacteria strain were
20 obtained after the contact with the $[\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2]$ suspensions ($50 \mu\text{L}$ aliquot) *via* confocal
21 microscopy using a Confocal SP5 (Leica Microsystems, Germany). The bacteria were
22 stained with a LIVE/DEAD kit (Live/Dead BacLight Viability Kit, Thermo Fisher,
23 USA) where $10 \mu\text{L}$ of the fluorescent dye mixture ($10 \mu\text{L}$ of propidium iodide (PI) + 10
24 μL of Syto 9 in $980 \mu\text{L}$ of DMSO) were incubated with each bacterial strain during 30
25 min at RT (in dark). Green fluorescence determines the «*live*» bacteria (intact
26 membrane; Syto 9: live cells, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 480 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 500 \text{ nm}$) whereas the red intensity
27 indicates the «*dead*» cells (PI: dead cells, $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 490 \text{ nm}$; $\lambda_{\text{em}} = 635 \text{ nm}$).

26 2.10. Statistics:

28 The results of the different assays are represented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).
29 Ordinary Two-way ANOVA analysis of variance followed by a Tukey's multiple
30 comparison tests were carried out to determine significant differences using GraphPad
31 Prism 9.2 software (GraphPad Software, Inc., La Jolla, CA, USA). Each experiment
32 was performed at least three times ($n \geq 3$). In the graphs, the results are indicated as: * $P \leq$
33 0.05 , ** $P \leq 0.01$, *** $P \leq 0.001$ and **** $P \leq 0.0001$.

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

3.1. Synthesis and characterization of Cu(II) complex

The Cu(II) complex was synthesized by reaction between $\text{Cu}(\text{ClO}_4)_2 \cdot 6 \text{H}_2\text{O}$ and H_2L , in stoichiometric ratio 1:2. The elemental analysis data of complex **1** are in accordance with the general formulae: $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$. In the IR spectrum of the complex, significant changes are found comparing with the free ligand; one of the $\nu(\text{NH})$ bands disappears, indicating ligand deprotonation, and the $\nu(\text{C} = \text{N})$ band is found at lower frequencies, which supports that the coordination of Cu(II) has taken place through the nitrogen of the iminic group. The $\nu(\text{C} = \text{S})$ band also disappears and a new band arises at the region $\nu(\text{C}-\text{S})$ bands, which supports that the TSCN coordinates to the metal in its thiolate form. Indeed, the presence of water molecules in the complex structure is supported by FTIR spectrum (eg. antisymmetric & symmetric OH stretching at $3550\text{-}3200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; HOH bending at $1630\text{-}1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$; also, “librational modes” as consequences of rotational oscillations, restricted by the neighboring atomic interactions at $600\text{-}200 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) since some of the water molecules are not detectable by TGA (Figure S2)²⁵. The proposed structure, based on analytical and spectroscopic data,²⁶ was confirmed by single crystal X-ray diffraction (

Figure 2). The geometry around the central ion is a distorted square plane, with two deprotonated TSCNs bound in *trans* configuration forming two five-membered chelate rings through the S and N donor atoms.

Figure 2. A) Molecular structure of complex $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ showing the atom numbering of the TSCN core. Hydrogen atoms have been omitted for clarity. B) Molecules arrangement in the complex crystal structure.

The Cu-N and Cu-S binding distances (**Table 2**) are comparable with other reported Cu(II)-TSCN complexes. C-S bond distance at the coordinated ligand ($\sim 1.74 \text{ \AA}$) is within the expected range for a single-bond, confirming the thiolate TSCN's form.^{27,28} The C-N and N-N distances are intermediate between single and double bonds, confirming that charge is delocalized along the TSCN skeleton (

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12 **Figure 2A).**^{29,30}

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14 The crystalline packing of complex **1** is stabilized by intermolecular hydrogen bonds
15 between solvent molecules (dimethylsulfoxide, DMSO) and N4 of the ligands (N4··· O
16 = 2.794(4) Å) and, in addition, by the existence of a certain π - π stacking between the
17 aromatic rings of adjacent molecules, with 3.393 Å (
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32 **Figure 2B).**

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35 **Table 2.** Selected bond distances and angles for complex Cu(HL)₂.

Selected bond distances (Å)		Selected bond angles (deg)	
Cu1-S1	2.2337(11)	N1-Cu1-S1	85.02(9)
Cu1-N1	1.990(3)	N1-Pd1-S1'	96.11(9)
C1-S1	1.742(4)	N1-Pd1-N1'	168.61(12)
C1-N2	1.298(4)	S1-Pd1-S1'	159.14(6)
C2-N1	1.294(5)		
N1-N2	1.394(3)		

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59 **Figure 2**

3.2. Cu(II) complex stability in buffered solutions.

Speciation of metallic drugs in solution is known to increase in complexity with the use of coordinating solvents such as DMSO or more complex buffers such as simulated physiological media (Tris-HCl, phosphate-buffered solution-PBS, culture media, etc.) where the presence of diverse biological components (*e.g.* proteins, salts, electrolytes) could impact on the complex solubility and/or charge, which could compromise their performances. In some cases, the solvent can cause inactivation,³¹⁻³⁴ or the production of new species which may affect its efficiency.^{18,35} Hence, the identification of active species or the investigation of the physicochemical features under relevant environments (mainly, structural and colloidal stability) has become a mandatory study for the evaluation of potential therapeutically active drugs. In order to shed light on its biological activity and suitability for the desired antimicrobial purposes, the stability profile of Cu(HL)₂ complex was monitored in diverse physiological media up to 24 h, starting from the simplest such as aqueous solution (containing 1% of DMSO) or Tris-HCl/DMSO to more complex ones such as culture media (cellular or bacterial-*nutrient broth*, *NB*) by using UV-visible spectroscopy for the structural stability (see the Experimental section 3.1.-3.2.) or dynamic light scattering (DLS) for the colloidal stability (Experimental section 1, **Table S1**). A broad range of concentrations (up to 45 M, **Figure 3A**) were tested, showing a very slight decrease in absorbance at 6 h, which was maintained up to 24 h. This behavior is also in agreement with the observed hydrodynamic particle size and ζ -potential values determined by DLS: here the complex displayed a monodispersed size of 69 ± 22 with a negatively charged surface of -22 ± 2 mV, maintaining its colloidal performance after longer incubations times in aqueous solution (76 ± 26 nm & -22 mV at 24 h, respectively; **Table S1**).

Once we have learnt about the solution behavior of the compound, we study the lipophilicity of the ligand H₂L and the Cu complex Cu(HL)₂ for a better understanding of their potential permeability and metabolism impact (*e.g.* absorption, distribution, metabolism & excretion-*ADME*), which affect, in turn, their potency, selectivity &/or toxicity.³⁶ This key parameter is determined by their log *P* values using Tris buffer as a model for the aqueous phase, a common media to sustain the bacterial growing (*i.e.* pH control).³⁷ In both cases, the compounds showed a greater lipophilicity than 1 (log *P* values of 2.08 ± 0.03 and 2.95 ± 0.07 for H₂L and Cu(HL)₂, respectively), being slightly higher for the complex, which might be considered as positive for its potential cell internalization.⁴ Generally, a compound with an average log*P* level between 1- 4 is

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3 considered more likely to possess an optimal ADME physicochemical features for their
4 therapeutic performances.³⁸

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6 For the microbial assays, we have investigated more complex scenarios. Usually, any
7 material (including metallodrugs) dispersed in culture media, strongly interact with
8 proteins as a second biological target, adsorbing them on their surface (forming the so-
9 called protein corona), which affects their surface charge and, consequently, their stability
10 &/or biodistribution.^{39,40} As depicted in **Table S1**, this copper complex in presence of the
11 NB bacterial components (*e.g.* beef extract, peptone) exhibited an increase of the particle
12 size, displaying a higher aggregation after 24 h (142 vs. 241 nm, respectively). On the
13 other hand, when they interact with cell culture media (*e.g.* serum, antibiotics), Cu(HL)₂
14 seemed to partially stabilize the size maintaining the nanometric range in a fresh solution,
15 which slightly reach some aggregation after longer contact times (52 vs. 125 nm). In both
16 horc¹⁸ cases, the protein corona formation was also confirmed by the ζ -potential shift,
17 from a negative charge in aqueous solution to more neutral values at both incubation
18 times. A more neutral surface could explain the aggregation, observing similar colloidal
19 performances in recently reported TSCN-based Pd complexes.¹⁸

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21 In terms of structural stability of metal complexes acting as potential drugs, a broadly
22 protein model for evaluating metallodrug – protein interactions (the hen egg white
23 lysozyme - HEWL by UV-Vis, ESI mass spectrometry or X-Ray)^{41–43} is available. Highly
24 positively charged with hydrophobic residues, HEWL is known as a suitable protein
25 model for biological active binding examination,⁴⁴ giving insights of potential
26 aggregation processes in body fluids. Thus, we assess any potential change produced in
27 the UV spectrum of this lysozyme after the interaction with the Cu(HL)₂ complex upon
28 its dispersion in aquo buffered solution. In this case, the kinetic constant was determined
29 as a pseudo-first order reaction ($A=A_0-e^{(-k_{obs} t)}$), plotting the absorbance values at
30 280 nm (the characteristic absorption of proteins) as a function of time and fitted to an
31 exponential function (**Figure 3B**). The resulting absorbance of Cu(HL)₂ – HEWL showed
32 a progressive intensity decrease up to 24 h, very similar to the observed rate of the
33 cisplatin – HEWL control model⁴⁵ being also within the range of other similar complexes
34 with the β -amyloid special interaction reported previously by some of us.¹⁸

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Thus, $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ seems to possess adequate quality stable values under the desired physiological media.

Figure 3. A) UV-Visible spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ monitored from fresh to 24 h. B) UV/Vis absorption data of the complex $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ with lysozyme over the time and its binding rates (ratio used 3:1), plotted with the absorbance progress at $\lambda = 280$ nm monitored from fresh to 24 h.

3.3. Electrochemical profile.

For unveiling the redox potential performance, the electrochemical behavior of $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ complex was investigated by cyclic voltammetry, undertaking the measurement in the most similar condition to the cellular environment: requiring a mixture of solvents (*eg.* DMF/PBS, pH 7.4 (2:1 v/v; following reported procedures) due to its low aqueous solubility. The complex exhibited an irreversible reduction peak at (-0.64 V) *vs.* Ag/AgCl (Figure S4) that could be attributed to a $\text{Cu}^{\text{III/I}}$ process. Such value correlates to (-0.43 V) *vs.* NHE (normal hydrogen electrode), which is more negative than the reported redox potentials of common biological reducing agents, as for instance AA (ascorbic acid; +0.06V), NAC (N-acetylcysteine; -0.18 V) or GSH (reduced glutathione; -0.24V). Another pseudo-reversible process at more positive potentials ($E^{\circ}_{1/2}$ 0.37V in Ag/AgCl) has been displayed by the complex, which can be related to this $\text{Cu}^{\text{III/II}}$ process. Although it has been very difficult to establish a direct &/or accurate comparison with reported data (slightly difference of experimental set up),⁴⁶ the obtained redox potential suggests that the $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ complex could display resistance to the *in vivo* reduction.⁴⁷ Moreover, some

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3 authors have found similar values with copper square planar thiosemicarbazones
4 (NNS donors) complexes, suggesting also its ineffectiveness role for this redox
5 activity.⁴⁸
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8 **3.4. Antibacterial activity.**

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10 The treatment of human infectious diseases is currently running out of
11 effective antibiotics due to the extensive misuse or overuse, which has promoted an
12 increased rate of bacterial infection (mostly in the bloodstream), as for instance, the
13 case of the *E. coli* or *S. aureus* resistant strains to popular and prescribed medicines
14 such as cephalosporins or penicillin derivatives. Thus, the development of novel
15 action plans to constrain this AMR spreading have been highlighted by World Health
16 Organization (WHO).³
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19 In view of this emerging concern and taking in account the steady Cu(HL)₂ stability, the
20 potential antimicrobial approach of this metallodrug has been explored, selecting
21 *S. aureus* and *E. coli* as pathogenic bacterial models. However, prior to these assays,
22 we studied the potential biosafe dose of this complex in presence of 2 diverse cell lines,
23 both healthy and cancerous nature: 1) the colon adenocarcinoma Caco-2 cells
24 («colorectal cancer»), as the 3rd most frequent type of cancer and well-characterized
25 intestinal barrier model, extensively used over the past years for preclinical studies of
26 diverse therapeutic agents; and 2) the immunological HL-60 cell line, involved in
27 relevant biological processes, such as the cellular redox homeostasis (ROS). After 72
28 h-contact, a potential concentration-dependent cytotoxic effect was evidenced, being
29 the most elevated doses of Cu(HL)₂ (from 1.25 to 10 µM; **Figure S3**) the main
30 responsible to decrease the cellular viability regardless the cell origin. This findings are
31 in agreement with previous reported antiproliferative TSCN ligand activity obtained
32 by others derived Cu(II) complexes, showing higher Caco-2 cytotoxicity after 48 h
33 (IC₅₀ range of 0.68 – 1.07 µM).¹³ Thus, these outcomes underlined the need to select a
34 specific complex concentration range in order to achieve an effective performance with
35 minimal side effects.
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51 Bearing this in mind, diverse doses of Cu(HL)₂ were tested for an effective
52 antimicrobial selection, evaluating both the colony-forming units (CFU) and the
53 microbial enzymatic activity by the fluorescein diacetate hydrolysis assay (FDA) in
54 contact with SA and EC bacteria (see section 4 for further details). After distinct
55 incubation times (3, 6 and 20 h) in contact with a serial dilution of the complex (from 0
56 to 134 µM), a remarkable effect was observed for both strains: a statistically significant
57 growth inhibition of ~ 22 and 12% in SA and EC after 20 h were reached, respectively
58 (see **Figure S5**; p < 0.001). This high inhibition percentage (bordering CFU values of
59 0; p < 0.05) was provided by the MIC, namely as the minimum inhibitory
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3 which was estimated by 13 and 33 μM of $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ for SA and EC, respectively. This
4 obtained active dose ($\sim 17 \mu\text{M}$, providing 22 & 12% bacterial inhibition) is in the
5 same range of other reported TSCN-copper complexes.^{10,16} Thus, the achieved MIC
6 values of $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ complex seems to be a promising antimicrobial alternative.
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10 Once the antibacterial performance of this metallodrug was evidenced, in an attempt to
11 shed some light on the potential mechanism of action, we performed additional
12 enzymatic (FDA) and oxidative stress evaluation (ROS). ROS production (*e.g.* HO^\bullet , O_2^\bullet
13 $^-$, HO_2 species) is one of the most recognized growth inhibition processes, resulting the
14 majority in a bacterial death. Hence, a detailed investigation of the antibacterial profile
15 (CFU, FDA) along with the ROS generation of the most responsive dose of this
16 $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ complex was addressed (*i.e.* $17 \mu\text{M}$ as the mean value of both strains), being
17 compared with the same constituent proportions of the H_2L ligand and the metallic salt
18 (CuCl_2). In agreement with previous outcomes, the selected dose was able to inhibit the
19 formation of the SA colonies even at short times (3 h), being statistically significant
20 beyond 20 h (100%, *Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.* ; $p < 0.05$).
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24 In the case of the EC bacteria, a minor antibacterial effect was observed, being more
25 remarkable at longer times (6 & 20 h). In addition, it should be noted that here just the
26 copper precursor was able to induce a strong colony decrease in both strains regardless
27 the incubation time (100% inhibition *vs.* 0% of CuCl_2 & H_2L , respectively), pointing out
28 that the major role of the copper in the antibacterial effect of the complex.
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Figure 4. Colony-forming unit of *S. aureus* (dark column) and *E. coli* (white column) after 3, 6 or 20 h of contact with the selected active [Cu(HL)₂; 17 μM] concentration together with the corresponding amount of the following controls: free H₂L ligand, and CuCl₂·2H₂O precursor. In all cases, each sample value was normalized with a negative control (C-, 100% of bacterial viability). The statistical significance was disclosed as *p < 0.05.

In terms of the potential oxidative stress, the presence of Cu(HL)₂ did not seem to be involved in the induced antibacterial effect since no ROS production was observed over the time (Figure S6). This specific absence of oxidative species could be related by diverse concomitant factors such as i) previous reported data about their ineffectiveness role on the redox activity,⁴⁸ ii) the observed electrochemical behavior (Figure S4) as well as iii) the influence of the chosen dose (17 μM) or iv) the duration of the contact time (up to 20 h). On the other hand and regarding the enzymatic activity, the Cu(HL)₂ complex led to a relevant inhibition activity in both type of bacteria (~70 & 80% at SA & EC, respectively), prolonged over the time. In the case of the precursors, despite the H₂L ligand did not provide lower CFUs at any time point, it seems to affect the metabolism of both bacteria in a larger extent than the copper salt since a great activity loss was observed, even at shorter times (~90-94% & 93-99% time fluctuations in SA & EC

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3 strains, respectively; **Figure S6**). Thus, the bactericide action of the complex could be at
4 least partially explained by its enzymatic repercussion.

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6 For a better understanding of the biocidal effect of Cu(HL)₂, the live and dead bacteria
7 were discriminated by a LIVE/DEAD staining (green & red labelling, respectively),
8 observed with confocal microscopy at the longest contact time. Remarkably, upon 20 h
9 incubation, we evidenced the absence of viability in the few remaining bacteria,
10 decreasing not only the number of live cells but also the dead ones, which suggests a
11 stronger effect coming from the selected dose (
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18 Regarding the precursors' action, both ligand and Cu salt showed a drastic bacterial
19 mitigation (being more significant in *S. aureus*), observing a slight intense yellow color
20 («milder effect») in case of the copper than the fewer red staining (higher bacterial death
21 rate) in contact with the H₂L linker. Thus, a potential dual effect seems to be evidenced
22 for the achieved complementary action of the intact complex, demonstrating the stronger
23 antibacterial effect against both strains. The higher permeability rate in case of non-rigid
24 wall of *S. aureus* could be associated with the *time response – effect* of each component
25 in contact with each specific bacterial strain, as for instance, the impact of the lipophilic
26 character. In other words, fluctuations on the component penetration &/or retention rates
27 («*permeability coefficient*») could be closely associated with particular molecular
28 descriptors (*e.g.* molecular mass, hydrophobicity, hydrogen bonding) along with the
29 nature of each bacterial wall structure, displaying here the strongest effect in case of SA
30 due to the absence of capsule formation in comparison with the rigid cellular wall of *E.*
31 *Coli*.^{49,50} Despite it has been already reported diverse capabilities of bacterial cell lysis
32 and resulting performance efficacies depending on the thiosemicarbazone derived ligands
33 (*e.g.* lipopolysaccharide (LPS) instability, membrane disruption), the action mechanism
34 or the associated cellular response remains still unexplored.
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Figure 5. Fluorescence LIVE/DEAD confocal images of sessile *E. coli* and *S. aureus* on cover glasses surface after 20 h of contact with $\text{Cu}(\text{HL})_2$ complex at the concentration of $17 \mu\text{M}$. Moreover, both strain controls and their complex constituents (CuCl_2 and free H_2L ligand) were also depicted for better comparison. The scale bar corresponds to $50 \mu\text{m}$. All the images were taken at 63X.

4. CONCLUSIONS

We have reported the synthesis of a novel effective antibacterial copper–thiosemicarbazone complex, demonstrating their stability, lipophilicity and performance under simulated physiological media.

A significant growth inhibition of ~ 22 and 12% in SA and EC after 20 h was respectively evidenced, partially related to the enzymatic inhibition observed in both type of bacteria over the time (~ 70 & 80% at SA & EC, respectively) and observing, in addition, an absence of viable bacteria by confocal microscopy.

Despite these preliminary data has been achieved under no cellular infection environment, clearly indicate the promising application of these TSCN-copper complexes as effective antibacterial agents since an active dose has been evidenced (in same inhibitory range or lower than other reported complexes or generic antibiotics such as Amoxicillin),⁵¹ open new horizons for alternative/unconventional biocompatible therapies of infectious diseases.

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Supporting Information

Figures, tables and detailed experimental parameters obtained by the NMR data, physiological stability, biosafety profile and the antibacterial effect have been here included. This material is available free of charge at <https://pubs.acs.org/doi/XXX>.

Table of Contents

David Fabra, Georgiana Amariei, Daniel Ruiz, Ana I Matesanz, Roberto Rosal, Adoración G. Quiroga, Patricia Horcajada, and Tania Hidalgo.

Proving the antimicrobial therapeutic activity on a new copper thiosemicarbazone complex

